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About P2GreenN

P2GreenN's ambition is to foster the paradigm shift in our current linearly organised urban blue infrastructure and agricultural nutrient management towards circular clean tech value chains that reduce N and P emissions. P2GreenN aims to develop innovative circular nutrient management systems that

- use wastewater and human urine and faeces from urban areas as a valuable resource,
- recycling N and P via four innovative clean technologies in three pilot regions into bio-based fertilisers,
- which are used for food production in agriculture across Europe, reducing dependencies on current mineral fertilisers.

P2GreenN's fertilisers can support farmers in reducing the amount of chemical fertilisers used thereby contributing to sustainable land management whilst maintaining yield.

Funded by
the European Union

P2GreenN solutions will reduce fresh-water consumption for irrigation by using reclaimed water and simultaneously providing the required plant nutrients.

Just like manure from livestock is used as fertiliser P2Green is working on turning human excreta into safe and high-quality circular fertilizers for farmers.

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Policy Brief

